

BLENDING OF BIOBASED FILLERS IN THERMOPLASTICS TO YIELD CONSISTENT PROPERTIES

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1 General Introduction

Recent research has been focused on the incorporation of a variety of agricultural by-products as fillers in a variety of thermoplastics [1-7]. Currently, one of the largest hurdles in gaining greater acceptance of biomass fillers in the plastics industry is that natural fillers are perceived as inherently having quality and consistency issues. If the means to accurately show relationships between constituent content and composite mechanical performance can be obtained, then the blending of biomass sources to design properties can also occur.

For example, quality checks of biomass fillers being used could be set up at specified intervals, with subsequent variations of biomass blend ratios being utilized to maintain product consistency. This mitigates concerns about inconsistency existing in a single biomass source, and places natural fillers on the same platform as mineral fillers which can yield consistent final parts.

By demonstrating accurate prediction of composite properties based on filler makeup, and not just experimentally derived values for a particular filler source, would potentially allow larger scale up of industrial usage. Among other advantages, the ability to alter biomass sources as necessary due to availability or cost, with the confidence that in doing so there would be no change in properties of a product line, would promote further product development. Hybrid blending of multiple feedstock sources would also be a possibility, with the end goal of being able to create consistent properties in blends that do not maintain consistent filler sources.

In this study, agricultural fillers derived from sunflower hull, sugarbeet pulp, oat hull, corn cob, corn chaff, and distiller dried grains with solubles (DDGS) were added at 20% w/w, both as lone fillers

and as hybrid blends, into three matrices. These matrices were acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polypropylene (PP), and PP with maleic anhydride grafted PP (MAPP) as a surface compatibilizer. The role of constituents that makeup the fillers, including cellulose, lignin, and protein and fat were examined, as are shown for a number of fillers in Table 1. The results present a case for the applicability of predictable behavior between hybrid blends of multiple filler types with given global constituent levels, compared to single filler types of given constituent contents.

2 Experimental

The ABS used in this work had a density of 1.05 g/cm³ and a melt flow rate of 18 g/10 min. It was produced by IRPC Public Company Limited, Thailand under the trade name Porene ABS SP100. The PP used in this work was a homopolymer PP, with a density of 0.905 g/cm³ and melt flow rate of 30 g/10 min. It was produced by Total Petrochemicals, USA under the trade name TOTAL Polypropylene 3825. Finally, the surface compatibilizer used in this study was a maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (MAPP), trade name Polybond 3200 by Chemtura, USA. It has a 1.0% w/w maleic anhydride content, a density of 0.910 g/cm³, and a melt flow rate of 115 g/10 min.

Composite blends as specified in the test matrices were created by melt blending the respective fillers, base matrix thermoplastic pellets, and any required compatibilizer using a co-rotating twin screw extruder (Leistritz Micro-18/GL-40D). In the event of compatibilizer use, a strict ratio of 10:1 filler to compatibilizer mass ratio was maintained.

The pelletized composite blends were subsequently dried for a minimum of 12 hours at 80°C. After drying, the composite pellets were then injection

molded into final test specimens using a 50 ton Technoplas, Inc. SIM 5080 injection molder.

Tensile mechanical testing to determine tensile strength and elastic modulus was performed in displacement control at a rate of 5 mm/min, according to ASTM standard D638 on a minimum of 5 specimens per sample set. An Instron model 5567 load frame with a 2 kN load cell was used for the load testing, and strain was collected using an MTS extensometer with a 50 mm gauge length, model 632.35B-200.

3 Elastic Modulus

Analysis of filled ABS and PP (with and without a surface compatibilizer agent) show that there are relationships between constituent makeup and overall composite modulus performance.

For most constituents, such as hemicellulose, lignin, starch, and ash content, no discernible trends or relationships appear to correlate to changes in elastic modulus. Most surprisingly, cellulose, despite its crystalline structure, was not shown to hold a strong significant connection (Fig. 1). Instead, the most concrete correlation between composite modulus performance and constituent content was seen due to protein and fat content (Fig. 2). As fat and protein content increases in both single filler reinforced composites and hybrid blends consisting of multiple different constituents, resultant composite modulus is shown to decrease.

These results demonstrate that there are observable, and thus important differences in composite blend modulus performance that are influenced by the constituent makeup of the fillers used. It is important to note that this correlative trend, and the choice to focus upon protein and fat, does not necessarily indicate direct causation in resultant modulus.

Protein and fat are both amorphous, short chain polymers with relatively weak bonds, and as such the degradative role upon filler (and subsequently composite) modulus observed is understandable. But cellulose levels should also theoretically result in increases in stiffness, due to their crystalline, long chain polymer structure. This is demonstrated in the small degree of trend correlating cellulose content and increases in composite modulus. As such, the

trends for any one constituent should not be considered a direct, perfect interactive resultant effect, but means of indicating broad trends in performance.

But the correlation found between decreases in modulus performance and increases in fat and protein content provide strong evidence that hybrid blends of multiple fillers should perform in comparable manners to similar fat and protein contents achieved by means of one filler alone. This demonstrates that modulus can be predicted using a multitude of agricultural fillers as long as fat and protein content is maintained consistent.

The adjustment for fat and protein content relies on the mass fraction of a given filler being multiplied by the volume content of a given filler within a composite. Due to this, care must be taken when creating blended systems of varying fillers to replicate consistent constituent contents to yield predictive properties. Analytical mechanical models for fiber and particulate composite materials operate with the assumption that the matrix is being modified by a given volume fraction of a fiber or filler. Volumetric loading is used because it provides the ability to directly relate the geometrical effects of the filler to a physical approximation. As such, variants of these models, which incorporate empirically derived multipliers and variables to create better fits, maintain use of volume fraction to relate filler effect to composite performance.

However, it is challenging to create blends at predicted volume fractions of filler. Especially when filler and polymer densities vary by less than fifty percent of one and another, as occurs frequently with thermoplastics filled with biobased particulate, maintaining a known mass fraction becomes much simpler than maintaining a known volume fraction of a filler. As such, industrial use of fillers is normally controlled through a mass fraction loading rather than volume fraction.

In order to use volume fraction predictive models in an industrial setting with mass loading controlled production, care must be taken to produce blends that recognize density changes as well as constituent content variations. The volume fraction of each filler

of the hybridized blend in a composite can be calculated by:

$$V_f = \frac{P_m M_f}{P_f(1-M_f)} \quad (1)$$

This creates the potential for problems in predicting the performance of hybrid blends of multiple fillers compared to a single filler source. The goal of a hybrid blend is to use the same mass loading of filler(s) into a plastic as would be done with a single filler, by achieving the same constituent contents based on mass ratio. However, not all fillers will hold similar densities. As such, even though mass ratios are maintained, equivalent volume fractions of filler will not necessarily be kept.

However, if it can be maintained that the filler densities used in hybridization are within 10% of each other, then the error in using an averaged density for combined filler matrix is negligible. Subsequently the assumption of one filler with an averaged density can be applied, allowing for a single constituent mass fraction for the entire system of fillers, as well as a single calculated filler volume fraction.

This is validated through examination of a volume fraction model's ability to predict the hybrid blends of the first test matrix used to determine constituent role. Table 2 shows the difference in results between experimentally determined elastic modulus values and the corresponding predicted modulus according to an assumed model which predicts modulus based on fat and protein content of a filler [8] for an ABS based bio-filled composite. The resultant root mean square error for the hybrid samples was calculated to be 207 MPa, which is comparable to the average standard deviation for the same specimen sets (184 MPa). It is also noted that the variance in the model versus experimental data was similar for both the hybrid blends of corn cob and DDGS, as well as the pure DDGS or pure corn cob loaded composites.

4 Tensile Strength Results

Analysis of filled ABS and PP showed that there were also strong relationships between constituent makeup and tensile strength. Like was observed for the modulus performance, cellulose content was surprisingly not shown to play as strong a role upon

the resultant strength of a composite (Fig. 3) compared to the role of fat and protein (Fig. 4).

While cellulose content and fat and protein content do have small correlative trends due to the nature of lignocellulosic material, the results show that bio-filled thermoplastic strength can be predicted by fat and protein content alone. However, this is only true for polymer matrices in which chemical compatibilization is not used to interact directly with the cellulose of the filler. As Figure 5 shows, when a compatibilizer is used, the interaction with the cellulose causes it to be the dominant constituent. As such, a strong trend of increased strength is observed with increases in cellulose content.

As occurs for the elastic modulus modeling, the adjustment for fat and protein content relies on the mass fraction of a filler being multiplied by the volume content of a given filler within a composite. Due to this, care must be taken when creating blended systems of varying fillers to replicate consistent constituent contents to yield predictive properties. As was emphasized in the elastic modulus model development, if it can be maintained that the filler densities used in hybridization are within ten percent of each other, then the error involved in using an averaged density for combined filler matrix will be negligible. Subsequently the assumption of one filler with an averaged density can be applied, allowing for a single constituent mass fraction for the entire system of fillers, as well as a single calculated filler volume fraction.

This is validated through examination of the model's ability to predict the hybrid blends of the first test matrix used to determine constituent role. Table 3 shows the difference in results between the experimentally determined tensile strength values and the corresponding predicted strength according to an assumed model which predicts composite strength based on the fat and protein content of a filler [8] loaded in a thermoplastic matrix. The resultant root mean square error for the hybrid samples calculates to be 2.05 MPa, which is slightly greater than the average standard deviation for the same experimental specimen sets, which was 0.88 MPa. However, the hybrid root mean square error is found to be lower than the calculated root mean square errors found for the ABS sample sets loaded

with just corn cob or DDGS, and as such validate the ability of a hybrid blend to be predictably used.

It should be noted that the same applicability exists for hybridization blending and the predictive capabilities of biobased thermoplastics when a surface modifier is used. Since the correlative trend shifts to being cellulose dominant, creating hybrid blends where a cellulose level is maintained will yield parts of similar strengths, which can also be predicted through the development of models [8].

5 Conclusions

It has been determined that the mechanical properties of resultant composites with biofiller loading can be directly related to the filler's constituent makeup. A direct correlation has been established between fat and protein content of a filler and the reduction of a filler's effect on composite modulus. A direct correlation between fat and protein content of a filler and resultant decreases in tensile strength performance of a composite blend, when no surface modification is in place, has also been established. Finally, in instances where a surface compatibilizer is used, a direct relationship between cellulose content and resultant tensile strength has also been found to exist.

Overall, this understanding allows for prediction of both single and hybrid blends biofiller loadings of thermoplastics. It also allows for the mixing of multiple filler sources into a hybrid filler system. This will allow the potential for more controlled and uniform composite production using these products, which should help significantly advance the viability of these natural materials in industry.

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Table 1. Biofiller Constituent Content

% w/w	Corn Cob	Corn Chaff	DDGS	Sunflower Hull
Cellulose	30.8	7.8	9.3	42.4
Hemicellulose	34.5	23.1	28.5	16.7
Lignin	4.5	0.9	1.7	21.7
Starch	5.6	35.3	1.4	0.0
Protein	2.8	0.6	3.0	2.5
Fat	0.2	3.1	11.0	1.7

Table 2. Hybrid Blend Loading of ABS - Modulus Comparison

DDGS/ Corn Cob	Experimental Modulus (MPa)	Modeled Modulus (MPa)
100/0	2910 ±250	2870
0/100	3475 ± 90	3170
50/50	2810 ±300	3070
75/25	3140 ± 75	2960
25/75	3240 ±200	3090

Table 3. Hybrid Blend Loading of ABS - Strength Comparison

DDGS/ Corn Cob	Experimentall Strength (MPa)	Modeled Strength (MPa)
100/0	27.6 ±0.5	30.8
0/100	36.0 ±0.1	34.7
50/50	30.2 ±0.2	32.2
75/25	29.2 ±0.2	31.4
25/75	32.9 ±0.2	33.6

Fig. 1. Effect of cellulose content on elastic modulus of PP at 20% w/w filler loading.

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Fig. 2. Effect of fat and protein content on elastic modulus of PP at 20% w/w filler loading.

Fig. 5. Effect of cellulose content on tensile strength of PP with MAPP addition at 20% w/w filler loading.

Fig. 3. Effect of cellulose content on tensile strength of ABS at 20% w/w filler loading.

Fig. 4. Effect of fat and protein content on tensile strength of ABS at 20% w/w filler loading.

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